

SELF-EDUCATION AS A PROBLEM IN THE PREVENTION OF ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOR

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of preventing the behavior of adolescents. The study reflects the age characteristics of adolescents and clarifies the specifics of self-education at this age. It has been proven that one of the means of preventing behavior is the organization of scientifically based work to develop the ability for self-education in adolescents.

Key words: adolescents, adolescence, adolescent behavior, pedagogical approach, prevention of adolescent behavior, self-education.

Introduction. The dynamism of social processes taking place in modern Ukraine and the crisis situation in many areas of public life inevitably lead to the spread of deviant forms of behavior [3, 5]. Deviant behavior is a system of actions or actions that contradict accepted moral or legal norms in society [1].

The initial forms of deviant behavior often appear in childhood or adolescence. This is explained both by the child's social status and the specifics of his age-related development. Violations of norms and rules by minors for the most part do not pose a significant social danger, since they are characterized by primitive methods of commission and have a pronounced childish motivation [2, 3]. But these violations are extremely dangerous because, in the absence of a timely response to them from parents, teachers, the public, law enforcement agencies, and social services, they can become more serious and systematic and contribute to the deepening of the social deformation of the individual [6, 7, 8].

This is confirmed by materials from statistical institutions at various levels, indicating a significant increase in teenage crime, drug addiction, alcoholism, and suicidal behavior [9, 11]. That is why there is an urgent need for scientists and practitioners to diagnose social deviations in the behavior of adolescents and develop effective methods of social influence on children with a tendency to deviant behavior, identify ways to improve family and school education, and develop recommendations for the prevention of teenage deviations.

Obviously, the priority in solving the problem of deviant behavior of the younger generation should be preventive measures aimed at preventing the occurrence, spread or exacerbation of negative social phenomena and their dangerous consequences. In our opinion, effective prevention of deviant behavior should take place on the basis of organizing scientifically based work on developing the ability for self-education in adolescents [10, 12, 13]. After all, it is easier for a person who is able to shape himself to overcome difficulties of both a social and personal nature, resist negative influences and regulate his behavior.

Conceptual approaches to determining the essence of teenage deviations are reflected in the works of G. Avanesov, S. Badmaev, Y. Gilinsky. Particular attention in scientific research is paid to the problem of preventing and correcting deviations in behavior (B. Almazov, A. Bovt, L. Grishchenko, V. Iliyuchuk, D. Kolesov). The works of such scientists as M. Ginzburg, G. Griбанова, I. Kozubovskaya, T. Kolesina, K. Lebedinskaya, N. Maksimova are devoted to the issues of preventing deviant behavior of adolescents. Problems of the methodology and theory of self-education, its relationship with education were considered by A. Aret, V. Galuzinsky, I. Kon, A. Kochetov, L. Ruvinsky. The works of R. Tarifyanov, S. Elkanov, M. Taychinov, etc. are devoted to various aspects of self-education in adolescence. The relevance of the problem raised is confirmed by the works of modern teachers I. Bekh, S. Grishchenko, S. Karpenchuk. Certain issues of a theoretical and methodological nature were the subject of dissertation research by N. Antonyuk, E. Bykova and A. Galenka.

However, in scientific works the role of self-education in preventing deviant behavior of adolescents is not sufficiently disclosed, which, given the relevance of this problem, determines the advisability of its study.

Self-education as a phenomenon has always been and continues to be of interest to psychologists, philosophers, and teachers. In the most general definition, self-education is a certain type of attitude, action towards oneself and one's own future from the point of view of compliance with certain moral standards [14, 16]. At the pedagogical level, the analysis of self-education is understood as self-change, self-development of a person [8, 15].

Thus, Z. Sh. Mamaraimova connects self-education with conscious and personality-controlled self-development activities, in which, according to the requirements of society, the goals and interests of the person himself, the strengths and abilities he has designed are formed [16, 18]. The scientist notes that self-education consolidates and deepens the results of education, continues and completes the efforts of teachers and parents, it is a condition for affirmation in life, the foundation for success in any business, through recognition by society [5, 17]. As a process of self-change, self-education presupposes a person's conscious transformation of himself, his bodily, mental powers and properties, and social qualities. This requires active action, self-confidence, the ability to concentrate, and firm confidence in achieving success [18].

Studying self-education, scientists note that its main components are self-knowledge, self-attitude and self-regulation, and the goal is self-improvement. Arising as a result and result of education, self-education develops and functions according to its own internal rules, according to which the individual defines certain goals, ideals in accordance with public and his own criteria, develops a program of work on himself, chooses methods and means of achieving the desired results, exercises self-control over process of self-education, makes the necessary adjustments [4, 7].

It should be emphasized that self-education can cover different areas of human development and activity. It can take the form of moral or physical self-education, emotional-volitional or intellectual, aesthetic or labor. A person cultivates certain qualities in himself depending on his plans, life direction or goals [2, 9,18].

The need for self-education and the possibility of its real implementation appear at a certain level of personal development. According to studies by O. Bodalev, O. Kovalev, I. Dontsov, A. Aret, V. Orzhekhovskaya, T. Khilko and others, this level is characteristic of adolescence. In physiological terms, the boundaries of adolescence approximately coincide with the education of children in grades 5-9, 10 of a general education school and cover the age from 11-12 to 14-15 years.

The main content and specific difference of adolescence is the transition from childhood to adulthood in all areas of child development. The importance of this age in ontogenesis is determined by the fact that it lays the general direction for the formation of moral and social instructions of the individual [7, 12, 13].

Scientists note that adolescence is a sensitive period for the development of a person's self-awareness. Adolescents develop an interest in themselves, the qualities of their personality, a need to evaluate, compare themselves with others, and understand their feelings and experiences. Based on the development of self-awareness, increased demands on themselves, a new position among peers and elders, they have a desire for self-education, which is updated in the process of working on themselves [8].

At the same time, in the scientific literature, adolescence is mentioned as difficult and contradictory. This is especially true for its first stages, when the process of puberty occurs and the restructuring of the body's hormonal system is associated with this. According to medical and psychological research, the result of the influence of endocrine gland hormones on the nervous system during this time period is an imbalance between the processes of excitation and inhibition, which is manifested in the increased excitability of a teenager, his emotional imbalance, vulnerability, and rapid mood changes. This age is characterized by a relatively low

level of intellectual development, personal immaturity, dependence on the requirements of the group and the value orientations accepted in it, and the presence of problems in collaborating with adults. The socio-psychological characteristics of adolescence leave their mark on the behavior of adolescents, create unique age-related patterns of behavior, form specifically adolescent behavioral reactions to interaction with the outside world, which serve as the basis for the formation of deviant forms of behavior that are more stable in nature.

The basis of pedagogical guidance of self-education is a specially selected meaning, which is based on individual and age-related needs and is embodied in a self-education program. The optimal choice of methods, techniques and organizational forms of pedagogical influence is also important. In our opinion, the following are effective in working with teenagers: ethical conversation, oral journal, viewing and discussion of books and films, writing creative works, competitions, debates, lectures, psychological and pedagogical workshops, trainings, techniques for mobilizing a teenager's internal strength to complete a task. activation of the target setting, contrast, stimulation of the teenager's personal dignity, demanding trust

Based on internal incentives for self-education, the teacher can use a system of means (debt to the team, status in the reference group, various types of reports, competitions with friends) that will encourage the teenager to work on himself. The main thing is that the teacher's word is combined with the teenager's demanding self-image, with his self-critical assessment of his actions, awareness of his shortcomings, and desire to get rid of them.

The effectiveness of work on organizing the self-education of schoolchildren depends on its systematic and structured nature. Scientists note that systematic and systematic teaching of the basics of personal self-organization to schoolchildren, their active involvement in the process of self-education provides a significant pedagogical and preventive effect:

- activates all types of activities and encourages reciprocal efforts in one's training, education and development, which helps to improve academic performance, discipline, organization, etc.;
- promotes effective self-knowledge, self-determination, self-realization;
- forms a high sense of responsibility for one's own behavior, optimizes the socialization of the individual, produces correct self-esteem, teaches reflection and prediction, and self-control of behavior;
- accelerates the formation of the dominant factor in personality development;
- subjective (thanks to this, a person fully uses all personal resources for self-improvement);
- removes from students their inherent resistance to pedagogical influence from the outside, making them self-critical and receptive to pedagogical requirements, which automatically accelerates civilized development;
- reliably prevents the commission of crimes and offenses by minors;
- significantly facilitates the work of a teacher, social educator, freeing them from the constant and unpleasant obligation to urge, control, force children to study, and behave correctly;
- allows the teacher to quickly and accurately identify the individual characteristics of children and more thoroughly manage the quality of learning and development of each of them.

Conclusions. So, self-education is an integral component of personality development and one of the effective means of preventing deviant behavior. Self-education helps a teenager to better understand himself, evaluate his capabilities, cope with laziness, overcome bad habits, promotes the effective assimilation of norms and rules of life, guides him to an independent and conscious choice of a future life path, actively refusing types of behavior that provoke conflict with society. The conducted research does not exhaust all aspects of the problem being studied. Additional scientific research is needed on the issue of training teaching staff to organize the self-education of adolescents.

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